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Abstract book

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Radiotherapy for lymphomas: one-year experience of single center

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Institution and Objective: The aim of this abstract is to present the one-year experience of our radiotherapy center in the treatment of lymphoma.

Materials and Methods: We included patients diagnosed with HL or NHL who started radiotherapy treatment between August 2022 and September 2023. Data included age, sex, type and localization of lymphoma, prescribed total dose of radiotherapy, radiation technique and radiological response after completion of treatment.

Results: In the investigated group of patients (n=35), there were 20 (57%) men and 15 women (43%) with a median age of 57 years at the time of diagnosis. According to anatomical localization, radiotherapy was performed in 24 (68%) patients with supradiaphragmatic lymphomas. Involved site radiotherapy (ISRT) was more often performed compared to involved field radiotherapy (IFRT). The median total irradiation dose in the ISRT group was 32.4 Gy, in contrast to 33 Gy in the IFRT group. The median daily dose in both groups was 1.8 Gy. IMRT and 3D CRT techniques were equally represented in the IFRT group, while the 3D CRT technique was more prevalent in the ISRT group. Grade I side effects were recorded in two patients of the IFRT and ISRT group, in both cases stomatitis. Thirty patients (86%) had a complete response, four patients (11%) had a partial response, and one patient (3%) had no response to radiotherapy.

Conclusion: Radiotherapy remains an important modality for lymphoma treatment. Reduction of doses and radiation volumes leads to better local tolerability with excellent response rates maintained.

Keywords: Hodgkin's lymphoma; non-Hodgkin's lymphoma; involved site radiotherapy; involved field radiotherapy

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